

Extended Abstract

Job-Related Training and Planned Retirement Age in Germany

Evidence from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS) 2021-2023

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Background

In light of population ageing and declining birth rates, many governments have implemented policies aimed at increasing the labour market participation of older workers (Hofäcker et al., 2016). Extending working lives is not only relevant for pension systems, but also for companies facing labour shortages and for individuals, as continued employment may support healthy aging (Staudinger et al., 2016; Mazzonna & Perracchi, 2012).

Retirement decisions are multifactorial, including individual, work-related, and family-related determinants (Fisher et al., 2016). If and when people retire depends on the individual ability, opportunity, and desire to continue working (de Wind et al., 2015). One factor potentially prolonging individual working life is job-related training, as training helps workers to stay up to date with developments (Hennekam, 2015). It is associated with improved performance, higher work motivation, and lower turnover intentions (De Grip & Sauermann, 2013; Hansson, 2009; Dysvik & Kuvaas, 2008). Training participation varies by age: Younger workers are offered training more often (Karpinska et al., 2015) and are on average more interested in training (Ng et al., 2010). This may be because of changing priorities across the work lifespan, as lifespan theories suggest that growth-related work motives decline with age (Kooij et al., 2011) and with shorter time horizons, workers focus on other aspects of the job (Kooij et al. 2011). However, it may also be a consequence of managers' as well as internalized age stereotypes at work (Posthuma & Campion, 2009).

Job-related training has been seen as a factor potentially associated with extending working lives. Apart from enhancing and updating skills, thereby increasing the ability and opportunity to keep working longer, training participation may also affect the motivation to prolong one's working life. Human capital theory suggests that investments in skills extend working lives in order for these investments to pay off (Becker, 1964; Ben-Porath, 1967). Moreover, participating in training activities may foster a feeling of reciprocity for the employer, increasing the willingness to remain employed longer (van de Grip et al., 2020).

The association between training and retirement planning may vary across the life course. Nevertheless, retirement decision-making becomes more concrete as individuals approach retirement (Feldman & Beehr, 2011). This implies that training may be particularly relevant during the phase when individuals actively assess their employability and remaining career horizon.

Empirical research on the association of job-related training and retirement (intentions) is limited and shows mixed results (e.g. Mäcken et al., 2022; Nägele et al., 2025; Henkens et al., 2014; Herrbach et al., 2009; Kristensen, 2012). One possible reason for the mixed findings is differences in national contexts as well as in how training (e.g. publicly funded only or general opportunities instead of actual training participation) and retirement

outcomes (e.g. preferred, planned, or actual retirement) are specified. Planned retirement age predicts actual retirement age relatively well (Engstler, 2004; Ilmakunnas & Ilmakunnas, 2018). Nevertheless, deviations differ systematically by race, education level, and birth cohort (Abrams et al., 2022) and can be influenced by unexpected events such as health shocks (Ilmakunnas & Ilmakunnas, 2018). Retirement planning can be understood as an interface between personal preferences and realities (Hasselhorn & Borchart, 2025).

Against this background, the present study investigates the association between job-related training and planned retirement age in Germany, addressing both cross-sectional differences and within-individual changes over time and assuming the following hypotheses:

H1: Employed individuals who participate in job-related training report a higher planned retirement age.

H2: Participation in job-related training is associated with an increase in planned retirement age over time.

It is important to note that possible associations of training participation and retirement intentions can have different explanations. Apart from a causal effect of training participation, it may also be that retirement intentions influence whether individuals participate in training, or that third variables, for example performance at work or specific health issues that we do not assess in our dataset, influence who is offered training or is able to participate.

Data and Methods

Analyses are based on data from the German Ageing Survey (DEAS), a nationally representative longitudinal study of individuals aged 40 and older (Klaus et al., 2017; Vogel et al., 2022). We used two recent waves (2020/21 and 2023) and restricted the sample to employed individuals (both employees and self-employed) aged 43–65. The cross-sectional analyses included 1,133 respondents, while the longitudinal analyses were based on 703 respondents observed in both waves.

The key dependent variable was planned retirement age, measured as the self-reported age at which individuals plan to stop working. The main independent variable was participation in job-related training, captured as a binary indicator of whether individuals attended any occupational training activities within the past three years. For the cross-sectional analyses, we estimated survey-weighted linear regression models with stepwise inclusion of control variables covering demographic characteristics, socioeconomic status, job-related factors, health, and work-related stressors. To examine changes over time, we estimated fixed-effects panel models that exploit within-individual variation between 2021 and 2023, incorporating time-varying controls analogous to those used in the cross-sectional analyses, as well as an indicator of external health shocks experienced within the past three years. Interaction terms between training participation and age group were included in both the cross-sectional and longitudinal analyses to test for life-course heterogeneity.

Results

The average planned retirement age in 2023 was 64.6 years, with significantly higher values among respondents aged 60 and above compared to younger age groups. Between 2021 and 2023, planned retirement age remained stable for nearly half of the sample, while increases were more common than decreases. Approximately 62% of respondents reported participating in job-related training within the past three years in 2023, with significantly lower participation rates observed among older age groups.

The cross-sectional regression analyses indicated that participation in job-related training was associated with a slightly higher planned retirement age. In the fully adjusted model, the difference amounted to approximately half a year. However, the magnitude of this association was small and sensitive to model specification. No interaction effects between training participation and age were observed. Sensitivity analyses further qualified these findings: the association disappeared when self-employed individuals were excluded and could not be replicated in earlier waves (2017 and 2021). Moreover, analyses incorporating training frequency revealed no clear dose–response relationship, with the observed association primarily driven by low levels of participation.

The fixed-effects analyses provided no evidence for a general within-individual effect of training participation on changes in planned retirement age. However, there was evidence of heterogeneity across age groups. Among individuals aged 55–59, participation in job-related training was associated with an increase in planned retirement age of approximately 0.45 years. In contrast, no significant associations were observed for younger or older individuals. The age-specific association remained robust when excluding self-employed individuals and, consistent with the cross-sectional findings, appeared to be driven mainly by low levels of training participation. At the same time, the results were sensitive to the operationalization of age groups: when age was defined based on 2023 rather than 2021, the association was no longer statistically significant.

Discussion and Conclusion

Overall, the findings provide limited support for the association between job-related training and planned retirement age. While cross-sectional analyses suggest a small positive association, this effect is not robust across model specification, samples, or time points. The longitudinal analyses highlight that training may matter primarily for individuals in their late 50s. This is consistent with theoretical perspectives emphasizing the importance of life-course timing in retirement decision-making (Feldman & Beehr, 2011). Training may reinforce perceptions of employability and work ability at a stage when retirement plans are still adjustable but already salient.

At the same time, the observed associations may reflect selection processes rather than causal effects. Individuals who intend to work longer may be more likely to invest in training, and employers may selectively offer training to individuals with higher productivity or better health.

In conclusion, job-related training does not appear to be a universal driver of later retirement planning. Its effects are modest, context-dependent, and concentrated in specific

stages of the late career. Future research should more explicitly address selection processes, explore causal mechanisms and the pathways through which job-related training shapes retirement planning.

Literature

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